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Activation of DDX6 by HPV16.

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Classical DDX activation occurs in response to nucleic acids. We found DDX6 activation in response to infection with HPV16 and with HPV16 L1 capsid infection, demonstrating DDX activation in response to a structural or morphologic aspect of the virion.